

Randomised Controlled Trial to Compare Safety and Efficacy of Propranolol with Flunarizine in Adult Patients Suffering from Migraine as Prophylactic Drugs

Dr.Abbhishek Garg^{1*}, Dr.Atal Sood², Dr.Amit Bhardwaj³, Dr.Sushama Sawaraj⁴

¹Junior Resident - 3rd Year, Department of Pharmacology, Dr.Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College & Hospital Kangra at Tanda (Himachal Pradesh) Pradesh 176001, India

²Professor and Head, Department of Pharmacology, Dr.Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College & Hospital Kangra at Tanda (Himachal Pradesh) Pradesh 176001, India

³Professor and Head, Department of Neurology, Dr.Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College & Hospital Kangra at Tanda (Himachal Pradesh) Pradesh 176001, India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Dr. Rajendra Prasad Government Medical College & Hospital Kangra at Tanda (Himachal Pradesh) Pradesh 176001, India

OPEN ACCESS

*Corresponding Author Dr.AbbhishekGarg

Junior Resident - 3rd Year,
Department of Pharmacology,
Dr.Rajendra Prasad
Government Medical College
& Hospital Kangra at Tanda
(Himachal Pradesh) Pradesh
176001, India

Received: 18-08-2024

Accepted: 14-10-2024

Available online: 19-10-2024

©Copyright: IJMPR Journal

ABSTRACT

Background: Migraine is a primary neurovascular headache disorder characterize by moderate to severe headaches, most often unilateral and generally associated with nausea and increased sensitivity to light and sound. Several factors can trigger migraine are probable contributing factors while others are possible or unproven such as: stress, hormonal changes, skipped meal, smoking, odour etc. Propranolol (non selective beta blocker) is the most common and one of the most effective first line medication used for migraine prophylaxis. Flunarizine (Calcium channel blocker) is acknowledged in numerous countries and included in numerous national guidelines for prophylaxis of migraine. We therefore intended to carry out this study and produce more data to support the choice of a medication for migraine prophylaxis that is both more effective and has a better safety profile. **Aim:** The aim of our study was to compare safety and efficacy of propranolol with flunarizine in adult patients suffering from migraine as prophylactic drugs. **Objectives:** 1) To evaluate safety and efficacy of propranolol. 2) To evaluate safety and efficacy of flunarizine. **Material and Methods:** This comparative, prospective, randomized, and academic interventional study was conducted in Department of Pharmacology and Department of Neurology at Dr. R.P.G.M.C. Kangra at Tanda, Himachal Pradesh in India. For this study total 78 patients of migraine were accessed for eligibility. After excluding 2 a total of 76 patients of aged 18-65 years, satisfying the eligibility criteria were randomized into 2 groups to receive either the Tablet Propranolol 40 mg per day for first 5 days then 40 mg twice a day for 2 months or Tablet Flunarizine 10 mg per day for 2 months. A general evaluation, and physical examination, routine investigations were performed on the first visit and repeated after every one month of treatment for next 2 months. Patient also assessed with VAS (Visual Analogue Scale) for headache intensity 1 (mild) to 10 (excruciating), to check extent of a patient's disease. **Results:** 89.2% of the participants in Group A and 52.8% of the study participants in Group B belonged to age group 18-40 years. In Group A, dizziness (n = 20) was the most common adverse effect associated with propranolol, while in Group B; tiredness (n = 3) and weight gain (n = 3) were the most common adverse effects associated with flunarizine. There was statistically significant increase in BMI after 2 months among patients who were in Group B than those who were in Group A (p=0.045). There was statistically significant difference in the mean (SD) Heart Rate value of participants in Group A (75.65± 5.1) and Group B (80.14 ± 5.9) at the end of 2nd month (p=0.001). Also, there was statistically significant improvement in headache frequency (p=0.01) headache intensity (p=0.004) and headache duration (p=0.04) in Group A as compare to Group B. **Conclusion:** Flunarizine was associated

with less adverse effects and Propranolol was associated with low headache frequency, headache intensity and headache duration as compared to flunarizine group.

Keywords: Migraine, Prophylaxis, Propranolol, Flunarizine, Compare, Safety, Efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a primary neurovascular headache disorder characterized by moderate to severe headaches, most often unilateral and generally associated with nausea and increased sensitivity to light and sound. It is derived from Greek word “hemicrania” later converted into Latin as “hemigranea” with a French translation of such term as “migraine [1].”

Several factors can trigger migraine are probable contributing factors while others are possible or unproven such as:

- Stress in 80% (probable factors)
- Hormonal changes in 65% during menstruation
- Skipped meals in 57% (probable factor)
- Weather changes in 53% (probable factors)
- Excessive or insufficient sleep in 50% (possible factor)
- Odors in 40% (perfumes, colognes, petroleum distillates)
- Exposure to lights in 38% (probable factor)
- Alcohol ingestion in 38% (wine as a probable factor)
- Smoking in 36% (unproven factor)

Numerous things, such as vigorous physical effort, lack of food and sleep, anxiety or stress, menstruation changes, sensory stimuli, and changes in the weather, can make migraines worse [2].

Headaches classification committee of the international headache society has classified migraines into following subtypes:

Migraine without aura is a recurrent headache attack of 4-72 hours, typically unilateral in location, pulsating in quality, moderate to severe in intensity, aggravated by physical activity and associated with nausea and light and sound sensitivity.

Migraine with aura has recurrent fully reversible attacks lasting minutes typically one or more of these unilateral symptoms: visual, sensory, speech and language, motor, brainstem and retinal, usually followed by headaches and migraine symptoms.

Chronic migraine is a headache that occurs on 15 or more days in a month for more than three months and has migraine features on at least eight or more days in a month.

Probable migraine is a symptomatic migraine attack that lacks one of the features required to fulfil the criteria for one of the above and does not meet the criteria for another types of headaches [3].

While the underlying mechanism of migraine involves the trigeminovascular system and its connections to the cranial autonomic reflex, which act as a feed-forward system to facilitate the acute attack, the primary issue with migraine is in the brain [4].

Propranolol is the most common and one of the most effective first line medication used for migraine prophylaxis. The starting dose is 40 mg and can go up to 320 mg daily. It may take up to 12 weeks at an adequate dose for therapeutic benefits to become apparent [5].

Flunarizine is a potent calcium channel blocker and has proven its efficacy in prophylactic management of migraine. It is started at different dose levels of either 5mg or 10 mg at bedtime [6].

With these backgrounds, the present study aims to focus on to find out that among two medicines which is most effective and safe to use.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study design: The study was conducted in Department of Pharmacology and Department of Neurology at Dr. R.P.G.M.C. Kangra at Tanda, Himachal Pradesh in India. Patients were selected on an outpatient department (OPD) basis. It was a comparative, prospective, randomized, and academic interventional study.

Study population: Adult migraine sufferers of age between 18-65 with informed consent from a range of socioeconomic backgrounds who have been diagnosed using diagnostic criteria and NCCT Head were taken as the study population.

Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion Criteria

- 1) Patients willing to give written informed consent.
- 2) Male and female outpatients between 18-65 years of age with documented history of migraine (with or without aura) acc. to HIS criteria.
- 3) Duration of at least 3 months.
- 4) Frequency of two or more migraine headache per month.
- 5) Currently not on any prophylactic medication in the last 1 month.
- 6) Patients' ability to fill a reliable headache diary successfully

Exclusion Criteria

- 1) Patients not willing to be part of the study.
- 2) Patients with h/o asthma, diabetes, renal, cardiovascular, liver, neoplastic disease, neurological and mental disorders are excluded.
- 3) Active alcohol users.
- 4) Patients allergic or with known contraindications to any of study drugs.
- 5) Patients who have already taken either of the above-mentioned migraine prophylactic drugs.
- 6) Previous unresponsiveness to more than two antimigraine prophylactic drugs.
- 7) NCCT Head suggesting of any other disease except migraine i.e., abnormal fundus etc.

Proposed Intervention

Patients were recruited according to eligibility criteria. After a written informed consent, the participants were assigned to one group either A or B, based on computer generated random numbers.

- Group A: Tablet Propranolol 40 mg per day for first 5 days then 40 mg twice a day for 2 months
- Group B: Tablet Flunarizine 10 mg per day for 2 months

Before initiating treatment, urine pregnancy test (UPT) was done in women of reproductive age group to rule out the pregnancy.

First visit of participants who did not take any prophylactic medication for past one month considering baseline period preceded the two months of active treatment phase. A general evaluation, and physical examination, routine investigations were performed on the first visit. Patient also assessed with VAS (Visual Analogue Scale) for headache intensity 1 (mild) to 10 (excruciating) disease. Patients were assessed monthly for next 2 months.

Daily headache diaries were given to each patient to record the number of migraine attacks, the pain severity by VAS and duration of attacks (hours). Diary data was summarised monthly.

Analysis of efficacy data and vital signs was conducted on eligible patients. Availability of baseline data i.e., data of first visit and data after visit of each month i.e., 1st and 2nd month were compared and set as the criteria for efficacy evaluability.

Investigations:

Following baseline investigations will be done and these investigations will be repeated after every 1 month of treatment (for safety).

Hb, Random Blood Sugar, Liver function tests (SGOT, SGPT, Serum Bilirubin,) Lipid profile (Serum Cholesterol, Serum TG, Serum HDL, Serum LDL,), Vital signs (BP, Heart rate, weight), BMI, ECG.

Patients were contacted telephonically on the next day of initiating the prophylactic treatment and enquired for any discomfort or side effects. Patients were also advised to report any serious adverse event during treatment period. Follow up of each patient were done monthly for 2 months. Adverse experience reported were recorded at each follow-up i.e. after each month for next 2 months. And if deemed necessary the medication was changed appropriately or stopped as per physician's advice.

Measurements of outcome

After two months of follow up, the results were evaluated using the following criteria:

Safety:

Any report of adverse events by the subjects during study. Any derangement in lab investigations from normal value.

Efficacy:

Patients having improvement in:

- Number of migraine attacks (Frequency)
- The pain severity by VAS (Intensity)
- Duration of attacks(hours).

Ethical approval and Clinical trial registration

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and Good Clinical Practice guidelines. The institutional ethical committee approval vide letter no. IEC/028/2023; dated 17/4/2023. Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants. The clinicalTrials.gov Identifier is CTRI/2023/06/053593 [Registered on: 06/06/2023]

RESULTS

Total 78 patients were accessed for eligibility. Patients were screened according to diagnostic criteria; out of which 2 were excluded as they did not meet up the required criteria.

Rest 76 were randomized into two groups resulting in 39 patients in Group A and 37 patients in Group B. Two patients of Group A and one patient from Group B were lost to follow-up due missed contact.37 in Group A and 36 in group B taken for analysis. An intention to treat analysis was applied over them and analysis have been presented as follow:

Table 1: Treatment arms

Group	Drug	Frequency
A	Propranolol	37
B	Flunarizine	36

Table 2: Comparison of Age group distribution of patients in both groups

Characteristics	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Age group			
18-40	33 (89.2%)	19 (52.8%)	0.001
>40	4 (10.8%)	17 (47.2%)	

Table 3: Comparison of Gender-wise distribution of patients in both groups

Gender	Group A (n=37)	Group B (n=36)	p value*
Male	11 (29.7%)	7 (19.4%)	0.308
Female	26 (70.3%)	29 (80.6%)	

SAFETY

Table 4: Comparison of Hb between both groups

Hemoglobin	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	13.07 ± 1.33	12.81 ± 1.10	0.36
1 month	13.25 ± 1.10	12.99 ± 1.05	0.29
2 months	13.40 ± 1.11	13.22 ± 0.92	0.45
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.009	Base line vs 1 month p=0.004	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.007	I month vs 2 months p=<0.001	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=<0.001	Baseline vs 2 months p=<0.001	

Figure 1: Comparison of Hb between both groups

Table 5: Comparison of RBS between both groups

Random Blood Sugar	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	116.2 ± 10.7	114.6 ± 12.7	0.55
1 month	112.6 ± 6.25	114.2 ± 8.19	0.35
2 months	111.1 ± 7.40	115.4 ± 8.85	0.02
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.060	Base line vs 1 month p=0.831	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.345	I month vs 2 months p=0.310	

Figure 2: Comparison of RBS between both groups

Table 6: Comparison of SGOT levels between two groups

SGOT	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	25.52 ± 6.14	24.08 ± 4.82	0.58
1 month	26.11 ± 5.67	24.13 ± 6.07	0.15
2 months	26.57 ± 5.69	24.53 ± 3.94	0.08
p value**	Base line vs 1 month p=0.189	Base line vs 1 month p=0.324	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.166	I month vs 2 months p=0.535	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.085	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.554	

Figure 3: Comparison of SGOT levels between two groups

Table 7: Comparison of SGPT levels between two groups

SGPT	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	26.03 ± 7.66	24.98± 6.71	0.53
1 month	27.19 ± 6.97	25.69 ±7.03	0.36
2 months	27.51±7.22	25.33 ±5.99	0.16
p value**	Base line vs 1 month p=0.119	Base line vs 1 month p=0.171	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.424	I month vs 2 months p=0.493	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.077	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.480	

Figure 4: Comparison of SGPT levels between two groups

Table 8: Comparison of Total Bilirubin levels between two groups

Total Bilirubin	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	0.54 ± 0.16	0.64 ± 0.21	0.04
1 month	0.57 ± 0.17	0.65 ± 0.17	0.06
2 months	0.64± 0.14	0.63 ± 0.13	0.96
p value**	Base line vs 1 month p=0.217	Base line vs 1 month p=0.613	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.002	I month vs 2 months p=0.608	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.000	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.939	

Figure 5: Comparison of Total Bilirubin levels between two groups

Table 9: Comparison of serum cholesterol levels between two groups

Serum cholesterol	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	161.6± 27.68	160.1 ± 33.46	0.83
1 month	158.43± 23.99	159.72 ± 27.35	0.83
2 months	160.95± 22.76	158.75 ± 24.12	0.69
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.271	Base line vs 1 month p=0.855	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.287	I month vs 2 months p=0.555	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.852	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.625	

Figure 6: Comparison of serum cholesterol levels between two groups

Table 10: Comparison of triglyceride levels between two groups

Triglycerides	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	103.97 ± 30.94	98.03 ± 32.1	0.33
1 month	107.08 ± 26.91	99.76 ± 31.7	0.10
2 months	109.73 ± 28.6	102.19 ± 30.4	0.03
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.697	Base line vs 1 month p=0.379	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.098	I month vs 2 months p=0.010	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.188	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.057	

Figure 7: Comparison of triglyceride levels between two groups

Table 11: Comparison of HDL levels between two groups

HDL	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	47.41 ± 11.3	49.56 ± 9.23	0.37
1 month	47.69 ± 10.43	49.16 ± 9.95	0.54
2 months	48.31 ± 11.1	48.76 ± 11.1	0.86

p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.657	Base line vs 1 month p=0.734	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.614	I month vs 2 months p=0.281	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.554	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.320	

Figure 8: Comparison of HDL levels between two groups

Table 12: Comparison of LDL levels between two groups

LDL	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	94.83 ± 18.2	85.98 ± 20.6	0.047
1 month	95.17 ± 16.94	87.3 ± 17.26	0.016
2 months	96.7 ± 18.02	88.95 ± 13.7	0.002
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=0.640	Base line vs 1 month p=0.793	
	I month vs 2 months p=0.094	I month vs 2 months p=0.824	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.088	Baseline vs 2 months p=0.698	

Figure 9: Comparison of LDL levels between two groups

Table 13: Comparison of SBP between two groups

Systolic Blood Pressure	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	123.43 ± 8.9	125.11 ± 9.2	0.43
1 month	119.51 ± 7.7	123.92 ± 8.7	0.02
2 months	116.16 ± 6.6	121.58 ± 8.2	0.003

Figure 10: Comparison of SBP between two groups

Table 14: Comparison of DBP between two groups

Diastolic Blood Pressure	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	71.81 ± 4.0	72.36 ± 6.3	0.66
1 month	70.59 ± 3.98	72.81 ± 5.42	0.051
2 months	68.81 ± 4.1	71.78 ± 4.7	0.006

Figure 11: Comparison of DBP between two groups

Table 15: Comparison of Heart Rate between two groups

Heart Rate	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	81.73 ± 5.8	80.86 ± 6.7	0.55
1 month	78.84 ± 5.0	80.17 ± 6.3	0.32
2 months	75.65 ± 5.1	80.14 ± 5.9	0.001

Figure 12: Comparison of heart rate between two groups

Table 16: Comparison of BMI between two groups

BMI	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value *
Baseline	22.03 ± 2.81	22.55 ± 2.40	0.488
1 month	22.12 ± 2.83	23.2 ± 2.35	0.06
2 months	22.42 ± 2.71	23.8± 2.32	0.045
p value** intragroup	Base line vs 1 month p=<0.001	Base line vs 1 month p=<0.001	
	I month vs 2 monthsp= 0.002	I month vs 2 months p=0.001	
	Baseline vs 2 months p=<0.001	Baseline vs 2 months p=<0.001	

Figure 13: Comparison of BMI between two groups

EFFICACY

Table 17: Comparison of Headache Frequency per month between two groups

Headache frequency	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value *
Baseline	6.54 ± 2.17	7.19 ± 3.18	0.29
1 month	4.00 ± 1.92	4.86 ± 2.35	0.09
2 months	2.00 ± 2.35	3.47 ± 2.85	0.01

Figure 14: Comparison of Headache Frequency per month between two groups

Table 18: Comparison of Headache Intensity (1-10) between two groups

Headache intensity	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	7.59 ± 1.86	8.42 ± 1.68	0.04
1 month	4.95 ± 2.44	6.22 ± 2.05	0.01
2 months	2.49 ± 3.05	4.50 ± 2.69	0.004

Figure 15: Comparison of Headache Intensity between two groups

Table 19: Comparison of Headache duration per day (in hours) between two groups

Headache duration	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value*
Baseline	9.51 ± 6.01	10.03 ± 9.39	0.77
1 month	5.27 ± 4.43	6.03 ± 4.33	0.46
2 months	2.40 ± 3.18	4.05 ± 3.76	0.04

Figure 16: Comparison of Headache duration per day (in hours) between two groups

Table 20: Comparison of treatment emergent adverse events between two groups

Side effects	Group A (n= 37)	Group B (n= 36)	p value
Decrease athletic performance	1	0	<0.001
Dizziness	20	0	
Drowsiness	0	2	
Fatigue	1	0	
GI upset	1	0	

Low mood	2	1
Sedation, weight gain	0	1
Tiredness	0	3
Weight Gain	0	3
Weight Gain, tiredness	0	1
No Side effect	12	25

Figure 17: Comparison of treatment emergent adverse events between two groups

DISCUSSION

Total 78 patients were assessed for eligibility but after fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria total of 76 patients who were confirmed diagnosis with ICHD3 criteria and NCCT head enrolled in the study. Patients were divided into two groups; Group A received Tablet Propranolol 40 mg per day for first 5 days then subsequently 40 mg twice a day and Group B received Tablet Flunarizine 10 mg once daily for 2 months.

In our study out of total 76 enrolled patients; 33(89.2%) patients in Group A and 19 (52.8%) patients in Group B belonged to age group 18-40 years. Also 26(70.3%) patients in Group A and 29(80.6%) patients in Group B were females.

Safiri S *et al.*, in 2019, concluded that the number of YLDs (Years lived with disease) started increasing from birth, they peaked in the 30–34 age group and then gradually declined for both sexes and prevalence of migraine was higher in females, than in males, across all age groups [7]. This study is in concurrence with our study. There was increase in Hb (in both groups) after 1 month and 2 months.

SAFETY

The study found that there was statistically significant increase in random blood sugar after 2 months among patients who were in Group B than those who were in Group A ($p=0.02$).

A study by Groop *Let al.*, found that propranolol lowered the mean basal glucagon concentrations and induced a more pronounced reduction of plasma glucagon thus increasing blood glucose concentrations [8]. Both the drugs were found to safe with regards to liver function test. Similar results were found in study done by Dakhale G, Sharma V, Thakre M, Kalikar M. that LFT were within normal range after propranolol therapy [9].

The study found that triglyceride levels were statistically significantly more in Group A propranolol than Group B flunarizine ($p=0.03$) at two months & and LDL levels were significantly more in Group A than Group B at 1 month ($p=0.016$) and 2-month ($p=0.002$).

Our results are strongly supported by the fact that nonselective beta receptor antagonists like propranolol consistently reduce HDL (high-density lipoprotein) cholesterol, increase LDL (low-density lipoprotein) cholesterol, and increase triglycerides [10].

A study by Aronow WSet *et al.*, found that patients who were administered propranolol for 3 days to 1 year reported an increase in serum triglyceride levels and decrease in serum HDL cholesterol levels [11].

A study by Byington RP *et al.*, found that propranolol was found to increase serum triglyceride levels by about 17% (35 mg/dl) and lower serum HDL by 6% (approx. 3mg/dl) [12]. Systolic blood pressure was comparable in both groups at baseline ($p=0.43$).

There was statistically significant difference in the mean (SD) SBP value of participants in Group A (119.51 \pm 7.7) & (116.16 \pm 6.6) and Group B (123.92 \pm 8.7) & (121.58 \pm 8.2) at the end of 1st month ($p=0.02$) and 2nd month ($p=0.003$) follow up. Subsequently mean (SD) diastolic blood pressure values of patients in Group A (68.81 \pm 4.1) and Group B (71.78 \pm 4.7) at the end of 2nd month decreased and were statistically significant ($p=0.006$). The heart rate was also significantly less in Group A as compared to Group B at 2 months ($p=0.001$). A study by Gawel MJ *et al.*, found that propranolol treatment was associated with significantly decrease in blood pressure (systolic and diastolic) and heart rate and flunarizine had no effect on cardiovascular function [13]. The study also found statistically significant increase in BMI in both groups between baseline and at 1 month ($p<0.001$) and 2 months ($p<0.001$).

Subsequently the study found that there was statistically significant increase in BMI after 2 months among patients who were in Group B flunarizine than those who were in Group A propranolol ($p=0.04$).

A study by Gawel MJ *et al.*, reported that BMI increased to a statistically significant more among patients taking either flunarizine (baseline 24.3 to termination 25.3 kg/m²) as compared to participants who were on propranolol prophylaxis (baseline 25.0 to termination 26.0 kg/m²) [13]. These studies are in accordance to present study.

EFFICACY

There was statistically significant difference in less frequency of headache among participants who were in Group A (2.00 \pm 2.35) as compared to Group B (3.47 \pm 2.85) after 2 months ($p=0.01$) follow up. Less Intensity of headache among participants who were in Group A as compared to Group B after 1 and 2 months follow up ($p=0.004$). Subsequently less duration of headache among participants who were in Group A (2.40 \pm 3.18) hours as compared to Group B (4.05 \pm 3.76) hours after 2 months follow up ($p=0.04$). However, both groups showed statistically significant ($p<0.01$) decline in frequency, intensity, and duration of headache episodes over a period. A study by Ashtari F *et al.*, found that both low-dose topiramate (50mg/day) and propranolol (80mg/day) for 8 weeks could significantly reduce migraine headache frequency, intensity, and duration. However, compared with propranolol, low-dose topiramate showed better results [14]. Another study by Fallah R *et al.*, found that monthly frequency and severity and duration of headache decreased with topiramate from 13.88 \pm 8.4 to 4.13 \pm 2.26 attacks from 6.32 \pm 1.93 to 2.8 \pm 2.12 and from 2.36 \pm 1.72 to 0.56 \pm 0.5 hours respectively [15]. Monthly frequency, severity and duration of headache also decreased with propranolol from 16.2 \pm 6.74 to 8.8 \pm 4.55 attacks, from 6.1 \pm 1.54 to 4.8 \pm 1.6 and from 2.26 \pm 1.26 to 1.35 \pm 1.08 hours respectively however the topiramate was better prophylaxis as compared to propranolol. Study done by Gawel MJ *et al.*, found that propranolol as well as flunarizine decreased the frequency of migraine but did not affect the severity and duration of migraine [13].

A study conducted by Lai KL *et al.*, found that patients treated with flunarizine showed significant reductions in the number of total headache days (-4.9 vs -2.3, $p=0.12$) and migraine days (-4.3 vs -1.4, $p=0.01$) compared to those treated with topiramate [16].

A study by Luo N *et al.*, found that 66.7% patients in flunarizine group and 72.7% patients in topiramate group had at least 50% reduction in their monthly migraine frequency compared to baseline [17]. Our study is in discordant with the study done by Gawel MJ *et al.*, postulating that flunarizine do not affect the severity and duration of migraine [13]. In our study both propranolol and flunarizine decreases frequency, duration, and intensity of attack over months.

TREATMENT EMERGENT ADVERSE EVENTS

We found that propranolol in group A decreased athletic performance. Similar spectrum of decrease athletic performance or reduced physical capacity was reported by Stovner LJ *et al.*, in patients treated with propranolol [18]. This can be attributed to the fact that inhibiting β_2 receptors lowers blood supply to active skeletal muscle during submaximal activity and may minimize catecholamine-induced lipolysis and glucose metabolism activation, which

ultimately results in a decline in athletic performance [10]. The present study found that more than half of the patients who were in Group A experiences dizziness while around two third patients who were in Group B had no side effects. A study by Stovner LJ *et al.*, found that many patients on propranolol prophylaxis reported dizziness (35.8%) respiratory infections (35.8%), tiredness (16.1%) as side effects [18].

Propranolol is a non- selective beta blocker. It has negative chronotropic and negative inotropic effects leads to decrease heart rate. In blood vessel it also blocks vasodilation leads to decrease blood flow to muscles. It also inhibits glycogenolysis, gluconeogenesis and lipolysis lead to decrease glucose and free fatty acid which act as fuel to muscle. All these factors contribute to dizziness during propranolol therapy [10]. Two patients of flunarizine Group B experienced drowsiness as side effect. Similar results were found in long term, multi-centric trial conducted by Martínez-Lage JM; out of 1435 patients 289 patients reported drowsiness [19]. However, in our study none of patient in group A propranolol experienced drowsiness. The reason behind drowsiness caused by flunarizine is its additive histamine H1 receptor blocking property [20].

A study by Fallah Ret *al.*, reported that clinical side effects were seen in 18% (n=9) of Topiramate (hyperthermia in four, anorexia and weight loss in three and drowsiness in two study participants) and in 10% of Propranolol groups (mild hypotension in three and drowsiness in two study participants) [15].

In Group A, one patient taking propranolol complained of fatigue. Within the same group, one patient also experienced GI distress. Similar study done by Anker Stubberud *et al.*, supported that GI upset was more common in patient taking propranolol as compare to flunarizine [21]. A study by Gawel MJ *et al.*, reported that participants in propranolol group (n=3) reported weight gain, depression, and fatigue while flunarizine group (n=5) reported only weight gain, bloating, increased headache [13]. Two patients in Group A and one patient in Group B reported low mood during treatment period. This was in concurrence with the study done by Karsan N *et al.*, that mood changes or worsening of low mood in 17% (n = 33) patients received flunarizine [22]. In our study, one patient from flunarizine Group B experienced sedation. In 2019 meta-analysis done by Stubberud *et al.*, revealed similar results [21]. Flunarizine's ability to inhibit histamine (H1) is most likely the mechanism behind its sedative effects [20]. Weight gain was seen in 3 patients of flunarizine group. A study by Gawel MJ *et al.*, reported that participants in propranolol group (n=3) reported weight gain, depression, and fatigue while flunarizine group (n=5) reported only weight gain, bloating, increased headache [13].

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that compared to propranolol, flunarizine was associated with less adverse effects. Propranolol was associated with low headache frequency, headache intensity and headache duration as compared to flunarizine group.

REFERENCES

1. Rose, F. C. (1995). The history of migraine from Mesopotamian to Medieval times. *Cephalalgia*, 15(15_suppl), 1-3.
2. Martin, V. T., & Behbehani, M. M. (2001). Toward a rational understanding of migraine trigger factors. *Medical Clinics of North America*, 85(4), 911-941.
3. Arnold, M. (2018). Headache classification committee of the international headache society (IHS) the international classification of headache disorders. *Cephalalgia*, 38(1), 1-211.
4. Goadsby, P. J. (2012). Pathophysiology of migraine. *Annals of Indian Academy of Neurology*, 15(Suppl 1), S15-S22. doi: 10.4103/0972-2327.99993. PMID: 23024559; PMCID: PMC3444225.
5. Modi, S., & Lowder, D. M. (2006). Medications for migraine prophylaxis. *American family physician*, 73(1), 72-78. PMID: 16417067.
6. Francis, M. V., Singh, S., Goyal, V., & Keny, M. (2020). Flunarizine: a review of its role in migraine prophylaxis. *Int J Res Med Sci*, 8(2), 786.
7. Safiri, S., Pourfathi, H., Eagan, A., Mansournia, M. A., Khodayari, M. T., Sullman, M. J., ...& Kolahi, A. A. (2022). Global, regional, and national burden of migraine in 204 countries and territories, 1990 to 2019. *Pain*, 163(2), e293-e309.
8. Groop, L., Tötterman, K. J., Harno, K., & Gordin, A. (1983). Influence of Beta-Blocking Drugs on Glucose Metabolism in Hypertensive, Non-Diabetic Patients. *Acta Medica Scandinavica*, 213(1), 9-14.
9. Dakhale, G. N., Sharma, V. S., Thakre, M. N., & Kalikar, M. (2019). Low-dose sodium valproate versus low-dose propranolol in prophylaxis of common migraine headache: a randomized, prospective, parallel, open-label study. *Indian journal of pharmacology*, 51(4), 255-262.
10. Douglas, G. T., Steven, R. H., & Walter, J. (2023). Koch Adrenergic Agonists and Antagonists Laurence L. Brunton, Björn C. Knollmann editors. Goodman and Gilman's The pharmacological basis of therapeutics. 14th ed. New York: McGraw-Hills Education; p.274.

11. Aronow, W. S., Ahn, C., Mercado, A. D., & Epstein, S. (1994). Effect of propranolol versus no antiarrhythmic drug on serum lipids in patients with heart disease and complex ventricular arrhythmias. *Current therapeutic research*, 55(12), 1442-1445.
12. Byington, R. P., Worthy, J., Craven, T., & Furberg, C. D. (1990). Propranolol-induced lipid changes and their prognostic significance after a myocardial infarction: the Beta-Blocker Heart Attack Trial experience. *The American journal of cardiology*, 65(20), 1287-1291.
13. Gawel, M. J., Kreeft, J., Nelson, R. F., Simard, D., & Arnott, W. S. (1992). Comparison of the efficacy and safety of flunarizine to propranolol in the prophylaxis of migraine. *Canadian journal of neurological sciences*, 19(3), 340-345.
14. Ashtari, F., Shaygannejad, V., & Akbari, M. (2008). A double-blind, randomized trial of low-dose topiramate vs propranolol in migraine prophylaxis. *Acta neurologica Scandinavica*, 118(5), 301-305.
15. Fallah, R., Divanizadeh, M. S., Karimi, M., Mirouliaei, M., & Shamszadeh, A. (2013). Topiramate and propranolol for prophylaxis of migraine. *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics*, 80, 920-924.
16. Lai, K. L., Niddam, D. M., Fuh, J. L., Chen, S. P., Wang, Y. F., Chen, W. T., ... & Wang, S. J. (2017). Flunarizine versus topiramate for chronic migraine prophylaxis: a randomized trial. *Acta Neurologica Scandinavica*, 135(4), 476-483.
17. Luo, N., Di, W., Zhang, A., Wang, Y., Ding, M., Qi, W., ... & Fang, Y. (2012). A randomized, one-year clinical trial comparing the efficacy of topiramate, flunarizine, and a combination of flunarizine and topiramate in migraine prophylaxis. *Pain Medicine*, 13(1), 80-86.
18. Stovner, L. J., Linde, M., Gravdahl, G. B., Tronvik, E., Aamodt, A. H., Sand, T., & Hagen, K. (2014). A comparative study of candesartan versus propranolol for migraine prophylaxis: a randomised, triple-blind, placebo-controlled, double cross-over study. *Cephalalgia*, 34(7), 523-532.
19. Martínez-Lage, J. M. (1988). Flunarizine (Sibelium) in the prophylaxis of migraine. An open, long-term, multicenter trial. *Cephalalgia*, 8(8_suppl), 15-20. doi: 10.1177/03331024880080S804. PMID: 3052850.
20. Russo, M., De Rosa, M. A., Calisi, D., Consoli, S., Evangelista, G., Dono, F., ... & Sensi, S. L. (2022). Migraine pharmacological treatment and cognitive impairment: risks and benefits. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(19), 11418. doi: 10.3390/ijms231911418. PMID: 36232720; PMCID: PMC9569564.
21. Stubberud, A., Flaaen, N. M., McCrory, D. C., Pedersen, S. A., & Linde, M. (2019). Flunarizine as prophylaxis for episodic migraine: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Pain*, 160(4), 762-772. doi: 10.1097/j.pain.0000000000001456. PMID: 30699098.
22. Karsan, N., Palethorpe, D., Rattanawong, W., Marin, J. C., Bhola, R., & Goadsby, P. J. (2018). Flunarizine in migraine-related headache prevention: results from 200 patients treated in the UK. *European journal of neurology*, 25(6), 811-817. doi: 10.1111/ene.13621. Epub 2018 Apr 11. PMID: 29512871.